

O'ZBEKISTON
RESPUBLIKASI
TASHQI ISHLAR
VAZIRLIGI

JAHON
IQTISODIYOTI VA
DIPLOMATIYA
UNIVERSITETI

ROMAN-GERMAN TILLARI
KAFEDRASI
O'ZBEK VA RUS TILLARI
KAFEDRASI

TA'LIMDA TILLARNI O'QITISHNING MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI

**ПРОБЛЕМЫ ЯЗЫКОВОГО
ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ПУТИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЯ**

**PROBLEMS OF LANGUAGE
LEARNING AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM**

MAVZUSIDAGI XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

TOSHKENT 2025

Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyaning maqolalarini tahlil qilish va chop etishga tavsiya etish uchun tahririyat-noshirlik guruhi:

- Sh. Normatova - O‘zbek va rus tillari kafedrası dotsenti
- V.Mamatkasimova - Roman-german tillari kafedrası dotsenti
- N.Sharipova - O‘zbek var rus tillari kafedrası dotsenti
- Sh.Xasanova - Roman-german tillari kafedrası katta o‘qituvchisi
- H.Imamova - Roman-german tillari kafedrası dotsenti
- M.Abduraxmanova - O‘zbek var rus tillari kafedrası dotsenti
- G.Rofiyeva - Roman-german tillari kafedrası katta o‘qituvchisi

MUNDARIJA

JIDU PROREKTORINING ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARIGA QUTLOV NUTQI	7
BOSH MA'RUZALAR	9
G.M. RAHMATULLAYEVA (JIDU).	
К ВОПРОСУ О МЕТОДИЧЕСКИХ АСПЕКТАХ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК НЕРОДНОГО В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ	9
ULFET ZAKIR OGLU IBRAHIM (AZARBAIJAN UNIVERSITY OF LANGUAGES).	
THE SPECIFICITIES OF SOCIO-POLITICAL AND MEDIA TRANSLATION FROM FRENCH.....	16
M.A. MALLAYEV (JIDU).	
O'QITISHNING INNOVASION USULLARIDAN BIRI SIFATIDA OLIY O'QUV YURTLARIDA XORIJIY TIL DARSLARIDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	20
Sh.U. NORMATOVA (JIDU).	
G'OYADAN NASHRGA: ILMIY MAQOLA YOZISH YUZASIDAN AMALIY KO'RSATMALAR.....	33
V.A.MAMATKASIMOVA (JIDU).	
OLIJ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIJ VA SAMARALI METODLARI	39
M.D. ABDURAXMANOVA (JIDU).	
TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ZAMONAVIJ ELEKTRON DARSLIKLARNING O'RNI	45

I SHU'BA

ALEJANDRO PEREZ GUTIERREZ (ISPANIYA).	
PRINCIPALES DESAFÍOS DE LA ENSEÑANZA Y APRENDIZAJE DEL ESPAÑOL EN UZBEKISTÁN	50
H.K. IMAMOVA (JIDU).	
TURK TILINI O'QITISHDA "BUYURMAK" FE'LI MA'NOLARINING BERILISHI XUSUSIDA.....	55

SÜLEYMAN HILMI KIZILDAĞ (TURKIYA).

ÖZBEK ÖĞRENCİLERE TÜRKÇE ÖĞRETİMİNDE KARŞILAŞILAN
SORUNLAR.....61

M.A. MADRAXIMOVA (JIDU).

KOGNITIV TILSHUNOSLIKDA NUTQ MUAMMOSINING O'ZIGA XOS
XUSUSIYATLARI.....68

A.A. KURGANBAYEVA (MOSCOW STATE INSTITUTE OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS).

DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSLATION SKILLS SUPPORTED BY
TECHNOLOGY.....79

N.E.SANOYEVA (ChDPU).

MORFOLOGIK BILIMLARDA MINIMUM VA MAKSIMUMNI BELGILASH
OMILLARI.....85

WANG GUILIAN (JINING NORMAL UNIVERSITY, CHINA).

RESEARCH ON MULTILINGUAL TEACHING OF HISTORY COURSES IN CHINESE
UNIVERSITIES.....93

A.A ATABEKOVA (JIDU)

КАК ЧТЕНИЕ ПОМОГАЕТ РАЗВИВАТЬ КРИТИЧЕСКОЕ МЫШЛЕНИЕ ДЛЯ БУДУЩИХ
ДИПЛОМАТОВ.....102

II SHU'BA

**K.O'. FAYZIYEVA (OLIIY TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI HUZURIDAGI
BILIM VA MALAKALARNI BAHOLASH AGENTLIGI).**

INTEGRATING SOFT SKILLS INTO LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT: A PRAGMATIC APPROACH FOR
21ST CENTURY LEARNERS106

M.B. ISAKOVA (IMPULS TIBBIYOT INSTITUTI).

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC STUDY OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND
UZBEK.....111

Z.S. TESHABAYEVA (ChDPU).

MUSTAQIL TA'LIM LOYIHALARI ORQALI TALABALARNING KASBIY MAHORATLARINI
SHAKLLANTIRISH.....115

L. N. TANGRIYEVA (O'zMU)

BADIIY MATNDA BOG'LIQLIK HOSIL BO'LISHIDA LISONIY VOSITALARNING
AHAMIYATI119

Sh.M.ABDUGANIYEVA (JIDU)

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВИДЕОМАТЕРИАЛОВ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ
СТУДЕНТОВ.....125

M.D.TURSUNBOYEVA (ChDPU).

BOLALARNI MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTIGA IJTIMOIYLASHTIRISHDA OTA-ONA VA
TARBIYACHINING ROLI.....132

Z.S. TESHABAYEVA. (ChDPU).

OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA DIFFERENSIAL YONDOSHISHGA ASOSLANGAN TA'LIM
JARAYONINING XUSUSIYATLARI136

M.B.SADIKOVA (JIDU)

ВХОЖДЕНИЕ НОВЫХ СЛОВ В ЛЕКСИКУ ИСПАНСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.....144

S.Yu.SAIDAZIMOVA (JIDU)

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВОСПРИЯТИЯ И ПОНИМАНИЯ ТЕКСТОВ НА ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ
ЯЗЫКЕ.....148

NABILA NABIL TOKHY KANDIL (MISR)

DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND THEIR IMPACT ON DEVELOPING ARABIC
LANGUAGE TEACHING FOR NON-NATIVE SPEAKERS.....157

F.R.AZIZOVA (JIDU)

CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHDA YUZAGA KELADIGAN MUAMMOLAR VA
YECHIMLAR.....163

M.E. KODIROVA (ChDPU).

INNOVATSION TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILARNING
DIDAKTIK TAYYORGARLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....167

N.E.ShARIPOVA (JIDU)

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА В ОБЛАСТИ СУДЕБНОЙ
РИТОРИКИ.....172

III SHU'BA

N.A. ALTINBAYEV (TDSuU).

TURK TILINI O'QITISHD "OILA" KONSEPTINING O'RNI.....181

O.R. USMONOVA (TDYuU).

CONTEXTUAL VOCABULARY LEARNING IN LEGAL NEWS: A FUNCTIONAL APPROACH TO
TEACHING LEGAL ENGLISH.....187

N.T. ERGESHEVA (TDSuU).

АНАЛИЗ ПОДХОДОВ И МОДЕЛЕЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ И АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕЛЕЙ.....	194
T.I.URMONOVA (ChDPU).	
ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA BULAJAK PEDAGOGLARNING KASBIY MAHORATLARINI OSHIRISH ASPEKTLARI.....	200
IMRAN ELKHAN OGLU GULIYEV (AZARBAIJAN UNIVERSITY OF LANGUAGES).	
THE PRAGMATICS OF IRONY AND SARCASM IN FRENCH MEDIA TEXTS.....	207
N.A.SAIDOVA (JIDU)	
ISPAN TILIDAGI REKLAMALARDA YUMORDAN FOYDALANISH.....	212
S.M.ABDULLAYEVA (JIDU)	
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ РЕФЛЕКСИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ.....	220
N.Q. XAYRULLAYEVA (JIDU)	
ISPAN TILI O'QITISHIDA TARJIMA MUAMMOLARI: NAZARIY VA AMALIY ASOSLAR.....	226
E.A.KURTOVA (MOSCOW STATE INSTITUTE OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS).	
ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ И ИЗУЧЕНИИ ФРАНЦУЗСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В МГИМО-ТАШКЕНТ: ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА, НЕДОСТАТКИ	232
PAK SVETLANA VISSARIONOVNA (MOSCOW STATE INSTITUTE OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS).	
DIGITAL TOOLS FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES: THE CASE OF USING PADLET.....	241

IV SHU'BA

M.S. ISHANJANOVA (ADChTI).	
LINGVOKULTURAL KODLARNING NAZARIY TADQIQI.....	247
Sh.A. XASANOVA (JIDU).	
MADANIYATLARARO ALOQADA XORIJIY TILNING ROLI.....	251
G.R. ASATOVA (JIDU).	
ИСКУССТВО ПЕРЕВОДА - МОСТ МЕЖДУ ЯЗЫКОМ И КУЛЬТУРОЙ.....	257
N.M.MUZAFFAROVA (O'zMPU)	
XORIJIY TIL MASHG'ULOTLARIDA TALABALARNI "GAMIFICATION" TEXNOLOGIYASI ORQALI MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTGA O'RGATISH	264
S.M.ERGASHEVA (TDSHU)	

MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTDA NOVERBAL VOSITALARNING AHAMIYATI.....	268
MATANAT AHMEDOV ALIAGA GIZI (AZARBAIJAN UNIVERSITY OF LANGUAGES).	
ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ПОЭТИЧЕСКОГО ПЕРЕВОДА КАК МОСТ МЕЖДУ КУЛЬТУРАМИ.....	272
RAHMONOVA NEZRIN SULAYMON GIZI (AZARBAIJAN UNIVERSITY OF LANGUAGES)	
СЕЛЕКТИВНЫЙ ПЕРЕВОД В КОНТЕКСТЕ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ.....	279
Sh. A. ALOVETDINOVA (TDYuU)	
ПРАВОВОЙ СТАТУС ДИПЛОМАТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДСТАВИТЕЛЬСТВ И ВОПРОСЫ ИММУНИТЕТА.....	283

DIGITAL TOOLS FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES: THE CASE OF USING PADLET.

*Pak Svetlana Vissarionovna,
MGIMO – Tashkent campus,
Lecturer at the Department of Foreign Languages.
s.park@uzb.mgimo.ru.
+998507404760*

Abstract: The article examines the didactic potential of the Padlet online board as a tool for organizing modern foreign language instruction in higher education. It highlights the benefits and several downfalls of using Padlet to develop students' writing skills, motivation, and feedback literacy, as well as professional competencies, including translation skills. The paper is based on the author's teaching experience at MGIMO University in Tashkent with students from various academic directions and incorporates an overview of both Russian and international research. Particular attention is given to the pedagogical conditions necessary for the effective implementation of digital technologies into the language learning process.

Keywords: Padlet, digital learning, modern teaching tools, interactive platforms, foreign language, motivation, translation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tilni zamonaviy o'qitishda Padlet onlayn doskasining didaktik imkoniyatlari, xususan oliy ta'lim tizimidagi qo'llanilishi o'rganiladi. Padlet platformasidan foydalanish orqali talabalarning yozma nutq ko'nikmalarini, o'quv motivasiyasini, fikr-mulohazalarni qabul qilish savodxonligini hamda tarjima ko'nikmalarini o'z ichiga olgan kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishdagi afzalliklar va ayrim kamchiliklar yoritib beriladi. Maqola MGIMO Universitetining Toshkent filialida turli yo'nalishlarda tahsil olayotgan talabalar bilan olib borilgan muallifning amaliy dars tajribasiga asoslanadi hamda rus va xorijiy tadqiqotlar sharhini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Til o'qitish jarayoniga raqamli texnologiyalarni samarali joriy etish uchun zarur bo'lgan pedagogik shart-sharoitlarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Padlet, raqamli ta’lim, zamonaviy o‘qitish vositalari, interaktiv platformalar, xorijiy til, motivatsiya, tarjima.

At MGIMO Tashkent, as well as in many other higher education establishments of the Republic of Uzbekistan, digitalization of education today is accompanied by the active introduction of interactive technologies in the learning process, especially in teaching foreign languages. Interactive Web 2.0 platforms, such as Padlet, provide opportunities for collaborative work, exchange of ideas and visualization of educational content, which meets the current requirements for the formation of digital, linguistic and professional competences in students of higher education institutions. This means that students at these institutions should be taught not only facts and concepts as content, but also the more important skills of acquiring, analyzing, applying and creating new knowledge [DeWitt, 2025].

According to Deni & Zainal's research [Deni, 2018], Padlet is actively used in higher education institutions as a great tool for visualization and feedback organization. In Russian practice, as noted by Boyko E.N. et al. [Бойко, 2019:139], Padlet has shown itself to be a convenient tool for involving students in the process of learning and collaborative work. The purpose of this article is to present the possibilities of using Padlet in English language teaching on the example of real teaching cases at MGIMO-Tashkent.

In a General English course based on the Face2Face textbook, Padlet was used in a two-stage activity: oral and written. First, students discuss the situational dialogues proposed in the textbook orally, then each is asked to post follow-up questions or their own examples on Padlet board using the lexical and grammar structures studied. These possible scenarios of real-life conversation can be saved on the wall, furthermore, students have a chance to go back and revise the topic, for example, as a self-preparation for oral assessments.

This approach allows:

- Increase student motivation through active participation;

- Form writing competence;
- Compare and analyze peers' utterances;
- Develop skills of self-reflection and editing.

Fakhretdinova G.N. [Фахретдинова, 2023:298] emphasizes that Padlet is especially effective in collaborative work, where students get an opportunity not only to be creative, but also to see the contribution of other participants, which enhances their engagement.

Another example of implementing Padlet in my classes with Year 3 and Year 4 students of Private International Law and Business Informatics, when it was used in the aspect of translation. The instructor usually reads out some sentences in Russian, and students take turns posting their translations on the board or share their variants at the same time. The comments are followed by a discussion of legal terms, clarification of word choice and grammar structures, suggestions for alternative translations.

This form of work allows:

- Develop analytical thinking;
- Improve terminological accuracy;
- To see the variety of translation solutions;
- Engage in dialogue about the meaning and appropriateness of translations.

Research has shown that simply implementing this digital tool does not guarantee successful learning [Campbell, 2015:30]. Consequently, it is important to consider the following factors when working with this platform:

- Students' preparation for using the tool [Wozniak, 2009:195];
- The clarity of the assignments and the link to assessment activities [Yaakov, 2015:145];
- The possibility of anonymity [Deni, 2018];
- Providing feedback from the instructor (verbal or written).

I would like to share some of the benefits and limitations of using the Padlet digital whiteboard that I have personally encountered during my classes.

Advantages:

- User friendly and easy to access - this platform features an intuitive interface and does not require specialized technical skills, making it simply adaptable to different target audiences and educational goals.

- Instant visualization of materials - the platform has a significant image database and allows you to upload links to videos from internet resources;

- Collaborative and asynchronous working - the platform can be used simultaneously by an unlimited number of users;

- Increased student engagement and motivation - personal observations and data from the presented research studies and from user feedback [Padlet, 2025], showed interest and development of a sense of competition among students;

- Development of self-reflection and critical thinking skills - improvement of these skills when comparing answers between students, opportunity for discussion and reflection.

Downfalls:

- Distraction and lack of structure - open-ended assignments on the Padlet platform can deviate from the topic if not examined through. Boyko et al. [Бойко, 2019:140], noted that when students' autonomy increases, the risk of “content defocus” also increases. For example, when translating a text without clear rubric criteria and terminological glossaries, this leads to non-substantive discussions, overloading the blackboard with unnecessary information and reducing translation productivity.

- Over-reliance on written interaction - Padlet encourages predominantly written input. This limits the development of spontaneous speaking or listening skills unless they are accompanied by oral activities. For formats with a lot of spoken language (e.g. Face2Face textbook scripts), this creates a potential omission of language skills other than writing.

- Limited free version - the platform allows only 3 online spaces to be created at no cost [Padlet, 2025];

- Risk of abuse of anonymity. Anonymous posting, while useful for encouraging participation, can sometimes lead to unconstructive or off-topic posts.

In conclusion, Padlet is not a magic solution, but when used thoughtfully it becomes a powerful tool for interaction, experimentation and digital skills development in the foreign language classroom. However, it is important to remind that its success depends heavily on structured implementation, targeted learning and clear pedagogical goals. Without this, its effectiveness in developing complex language skills - especially in legal or academic English - may be limited or counterproductive.

References:

1. Бойко Е.Н., Никитина Е.Д., Логачева М.К. (2019). Интернет-технологии как современные средства обучения в вузе: практический опыт (на примере СИУ РАНХиГС) // Мир науки, культуры, образования. – № 1 (74). – С. 138–140.

2. Фахретдинова Г.Н. (2023). Применение онлайн-досок в процессе обучения иностранному языку для совместной работы студентов // Вестник ННГУ. – № 4(72). – С. 296–300.

3. Campbell, C., Monk, S. (2015). Introducing a learner response system to pre-service education students: Increasing student engagement. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 16(1), 25–36. DOI: [10.1177/1469787414558980] (<https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787414558980>).

4. Deni, A., Zainal, Z.I. (2018). Padlet as an Educational Tool: Pedagogical Considerations and Lessons Learnt. *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Education Technology and Computers (ICETC), Tokyo*. DOI: [10.1145/3290511.3290512] (<https://doi.org/10.1145/3290511.3290512>)

5. DeWitt D., Alias N., Siraj S. Collaborative learning: interactive debates using Padlet in a higher education institution // CORE. - URL: <https://core.ac.uk/reader/162014460> (дата обращения: 14.04.2025).

6. Padlet: обзор и отзывы пользователей [Электронный ресурс] // Software Advice. – URL: <https://www.softwareadvice.com/collaboration/padlet-profile/reviews/> (дата обращения: 14.04.2025).

7. Padlet: официальный сайт [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <https://padlet.com> (дата обращения: 14.04.2025).

8. Wozniak, H., Pizzica, J., Mahony, M.J. (2009). Stepping through the looking glass: A staged approach for developing reflective practitioners. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 25(2), 193–208. DOI: [10.14742/ajet.1132] (<https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.1132>)

9. Yaakov, A. (2015). Analysis of Technology Acceptance Model in Understanding University Students' Behavioural Intention to Use Web-based Interactive Tools. In: *SoTL Case Studies in Malaysian HEIs*, 141–150.